

Deliverable 7.2

Create Legal Entity for Sponsorship

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Contents

LIST OF ACRONYMS	4
1. INTRODUCTION	5
2. SUSTAINABILITY BUSINESS PLAN	5
2.1 SETTING UP A NOT-FOR-PROFIT ORGANISATION	6
3. PARTNERING WITH EUROBOTICS	7
3.1 NEXT STEPS	8
4. APPENDIX	9

List of acronyms

EU - European Union

ERL - European Robotics League

AISBL - Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif

ERF - European Robotics Forum

IROS - International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems

1. Introduction

The SciRoc project, funded by the EU-H2020 initiative, is supporting the introduction of robots in Smart Cities through European Robotics League (ERL) tournaments. The project began in February 2018 building on the success of previous EU-FP7/H2020 projects: RoCKIn, euRathlon, EuRoC and ROCKEU2. The project is due to complete in July 2022.

The aim of this report is to outline the next steps for SciRoc and the ERL beyond the project's completion date.

2. Sustainability Business Plan

When the project began in 2018, the Project Coordinator formulated a sustainability business plan to define the strategic roles within the project and an action plan to underpin the sustainable future of the ERL.

This plan outlines the annual running costs of the ERL, the activities that require support, the importance of income diversification, the necessity for sound and effective administration and a discussion into ways of generating money to support the ERL's future.

It became clear from this discussion that, if we are to provide for the sustainable future of the ERL, it will be necessary to create, or re-purpose, a corporate entity of some type which will act as the holder and distributor of project funds. It is highlighted in the original sustainability business plan that the income streams available to the ERL will in some part be determined by the legal structure of this entity, and the types of legal entities and the conditions of their operation will depend on the jurisdiction in which the entity is incorporated.

The type and jurisdiction of the entity will also determine the requirements for its governance structure, to some extent. In any case, the governance structure must provide for the fair and transparent distribution of funds, and approve the accounting procedures and reporting of the entity.

It was also noted that, at the time of writing, there was considerable uncertainty surrounding the details of the UK's future relationship with the EU and the ramifications of Brexit would need to be accounted for in making the decision of where to incorporate, and the legal structure of the entity.

The purpose of this Deliverable 7.2 is to create such a legal entity for raising and administering funds from sponsorship.

2.1 Setting up a not-for-profit organisation

Consortium members discussed a number of possibilities relating to the sustainability of the project, particularly the topic of raising and administering funds. The possibilities included:

- Collaborating with the European City of Culture.
- Set up a similar initiative to the F1 in Schools organisation that offers schoolchildren an exciting way to learn STEM subjects through Formula 1¹. Instead, we would focus on University students and the field of robotics and allow students to collect credits from their participation.
- Raising private funds where possible, for example by inviting high rank people (parliamentarians, decisions makers, etc.) to the 2021 Bologna event to encourage support of SciRoc in the future.
- Seek funding from the AIT project.
- Setting up a new not-for-profit organisation to manage the project and administer funds.
- Approach an existing not-for-profit organisation to work with.

It was decided that proceeding through a not-for-profit organisation was the best course of action however, given the overheads and difficulties in setting up a new organisation, we pursued the option to approach an existing one.

The Project Coordinator approached Alhub, a non-profit dedicated to connecting the AI community to the public by providing free, high-quality information². Sabine Hauer is a trustee of this organisation and part of the SciRoc Project Advisory Board. Alhub did not respond positively to the suggestion that it could act on behalf of the ERL in this way.

We also contacted the AI4EU foundation. Whilst their focus is to run and maintain their own platform, and so the foundation could not own the future of the ERL, it was thought that we could utilise their platform for dissemination purposes and to communicate with the scientific community. Unfortunately, the foundation were facing their own problems with the initial set up and so could not commit to a partnership with SciRoc.

A third possibility, and one that was highlighted in our original sustainability business plan, was to investigate the possibility that euRobotics AISBL (Association Internationale Sans But

¹ <https://www.f1inschools.co.uk/about.html>

² <https://aihub.org/about/>

Lucratif) will take on the role of the not-for-profit parent for the ERL. The benefit of brand association is obvious, and the ERL was always intended to be closely linked to euRobotics (the award ceremony for the overall winners of leagues occurs at the annual European Robotics Forum (ERF)).

3. Partnering with euRobotics

After initial discussions with board members at euRobotics, a meeting was scheduled in June 2021. The SciRoc Project Coordinator presented information to board members outlining the role of SciRoc in supporting the Smart City competitions and associated costs. Attendees from euRobotics expressed interest in the idea, but wanted further details on the complexity and overheads associated with the process of planning and delivering a Smart City event. In addition, they wanted to observe the success of the second Smart City event in Bologna, which would prove the model for delivery by a third party. It was felt that further information was needed to reduce the perceived risk in taking on this commitment.

A follow up meeting took place in November 2021 after the successful Bologna event. As agreed, the SciRoc Project Coordinator presented a full report on the process for organising the ERL Smart City competitions to euRobotics board members. (Please refer to Appendix A. for the full report.)

During this meeting the organisational report was reviewed and detailed discussions took place around the role of the SciRoc Consortium, expectations of euRobotics in continuing the project, plans for a third Smart City competition and possible host cities, the European Robotics League local tournaments, their purpose and plans for continuation. Key discussion points from this meeting included:

- The two sides of the SciRoc Project:
 1. The smaller ERL tournaments that take place in University laboratories, followed by an award ceremony every year at the ERF.
 2. The biennial larger scale Smart City competitions.
- The Smart City competitions are larger, more public events that have proven successful in attracting sponsorship. As we go forward and the name grows, it should be possible to attract international sponsors, which provide consistency of funding.
- The future of the smaller ERL tournaments is unclear. They do not bring sponsorship and so would need to fund themselves however, they are important in training teams and feeding momentum for the larger Smart City events.

- It is agreed by all meeting attendees that training is required but we could look into the possibility of holding smaller competitions at existing events such as the ERF, IROS, etc.

Please refer to Appendix B. for full meeting minutes.

3.1 Next steps

The outcome of the November meeting is positive. euRobotics board members recognise the value in the presented opportunity and are keen to move forward with sustaining the project beyond its July end date. In response to Deliverable 7.2, we therefore intend to move forward with euRobotics as an existing not-for-profit organisation and roll the future of the SciRoc endeavour into this entity.

euRobotics will look to hold the next Smart City competition in 2023, announcing a call for host cities to express their interest at the ERF (originally due to take place in March 2022). Interested candidates would then have two months to make their proposal, with a decision on the location for the 2023 Smart City event being decided in June 2022.

euRobotics board members will put together a proposal outlining this plan and present this to the rest of the board. Those present in the meeting are confident that, providing the finances work, the 24-member board will approve and we will have a solution to move forward.

The ERF has since been postponed to June 2022, so at present we await a final decision from the euRobotics board, who were reported on 25th January 2022 to be progressing towards ratifying and agreeing the proposal. This decision will be reported in our final review meeting and Period 3 report.

4. Appendix

Appendix A: SciRoc Organisation Report

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1BUVsnYsN1vAHTiDpWaO3LnBXiuBzOaQ?usp=sharing>

Appendix B: Minutes from euRobotics meeting, November 2021

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1BUVsnYsN1vAHTiDpWaO3LnBXiuBzOaQ?usp=sharing>